

Deliverable D5.1

Initial Cloud Infrastructure Deployment Blueprint

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CD	Continuous Deployment
CI	Continuous Integration
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
DBMS	Database Management System
DevOps	Development and Operations
DNS	Domain Name System
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
IaC	Infrastructure as Code

laaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
JS	JavaScript
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
LLM	Large Language Model
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
LUMIS	LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics
mTLS	Mutual Transport Layer Security
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PCSS	Poznańskie Centrum Superkomputerowo-Sieciowe
PV	Persistent Volume
PVC	Persistent Volume Claim
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RAM	Random Access Memory
SaaS	Software as a Service
SCRE	Semantic Content Retrieval Engine
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TLS	Transport Layer Security
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents an outline and implementation plan for the cloud infrastructure for the LUMEN project (more about the nature of this deliverable in the introductory "Scope of the document" chapter). The document is divided into three main chapters with an additional fourth chapter, which briefly describes potential plans for the next stages of the project.

The first chapter ("Understanding cloud infrastructure") provides a general overview of the cloud infrastructure concept. It introduces the most important ideas in this field,

explaining why cloud architecture is a valuable model today, both in technological and business contexts.

The second chapter (“Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PCSS) Platform as a Service (PaaS)”) describes the key elements of the Platform as a Service (PaaS) model offered by PCSS for the LUMEN project. PCSS servers constitute the infrastructure backbone for all LUMEN project components. While the first chapter is based on general knowledge and universal cloud infrastructure principles, the second chapter presents previously unpublished knowledge, referencing internal PCSS structures.

The third chapter (“PCSS PaaS as an infrastructure practice in LUMEN”), conceived in this text as a description of the proof of concept, has a similar, unique character. The first component hosted by PCSS for LUMEN is the GoTriple platform. GoTriple is the technological heart of the entire project (it is the foundation for White Label Platform) and was naturally chosen as the first component to be migrated to the PCSS servers. Chapter three (especially section 3.2) also outlines future plans in the context of infrastructure development in the LUMEN project. More information about the next steps and stages of development can be found in the dedicated chapter four.

Scope of the document

This deliverable provides the initial blueprint for the cloud infrastructure deployed for the LUMEN project. Its primary objective is to describe:

- the conceptual foundations of cloud infrastructure relevant to LUMEN (Section 1),
- the architecture and capabilities of the PCSS PaaS environment used as the backbone for LUMEN services (Section 2),
- the practical implementation of this infrastructure through the first full migration of a LUMEN component, the GoTriple platform, used as a proof of concept (Section 3.1),
- and the operational methodologies and best practices that guide infrastructure development in LUMEN (Section 1.5 and 3.2).

This document focuses exclusively on the infrastructure layer of LUMEN. The following topics are addressed in deliverables of other work packages:

- application-level design or development details (addressed in WP2, WP4 and WP6),
- semantic and governance models (addressed in WP2 and WP7),
- user-facing platform functionalities (addressed by the relevant WPs),
- long-term cost models, sustainability, or EOSC integration plans (addressed in WP7).

D5.1 establishes the technical baseline required for operating all LUMEN services on the PCSS PaaS. It describes the initial deployment model, the mechanisms available for scaling and securing services, and the infrastructure processes that will support the forthcoming components of the LUMEN architecture. Future deliverables in WP5 will build on this blueprint by expanding monitoring, automation, resilience strategies, and cross-component operational workflows as additional services are onboarded.

1. Understanding cloud infrastructure

The first section of this document is dedicated to the most important elements of a cloud infrastructure. The main goal of this chapter is to familiarize the reader with the basic concepts of this type of infrastructure, understand its unique features, and provide a quick overview of the most important technologies and services related to it.

1.1 What is a cloud infrastructure?

1.1.1 Basic cloud infrastructure concepts

A cloud infrastructure can be understood as the combination of physical computing resources and virtualized services that expose them on demand. Cloud infrastructures emerged to address the need for elastic, scalable resource provisioning without upfront hardware investment.

Cloud infrastructures expose compute, storage and networking capabilities as managed services. The cloud infrastructure provides both the physical and virtual parts of the architecture, offering clients intangible digital services. Therefore, the client does not need to invest in physical infrastructure.

This change sparked a revolution in the IT industry. It changed the approach not only to infrastructure management but also to working with various software. It was on the basis of the development of cloud infrastructure that the IT field of DevOps emerged (more on this in section 1.2), completely changing the way we understand infrastructure. As part of the cloud revolution, a way of thinking about infrastructure as code evolved – a kind of analogous process began to form between code management and infrastructure (as discussed in section 1.5.1).

Cloud infrastructure is therefore delivered as a ready-made set of services. Cloud providers offer both raw compute resources and higher-level managed services (databases, authentication, storage, pipelines, etc.).

This model can support cost optimisation depending on usage patterns and workload profiles, addressing the user's needs in an agile, demand driven, elastic approach. A key aspect of such a business model is the ability to fully focus on technological innovation rather than on managing a complex physical computer infrastructure¹.

¹ Arundel, J., Domingus, J., *Cloud Native DevOps with Kubernetes: Building, Deploying, and Scaling Modern Applications in the Cloud*, O'Reilly Media, 2019.

1.1.2 Kubernetes

Kubernetes – a term that appears repeatedly in this document – is a

'portable, extensible, open source platform for managing containerized workloads and services, that facilitates both declarative configuration and automation'².

This technology can be defined as a deployment orchestration platform designed to manage containerized applications (more on containerized applications in section 1.1.3).

Kubernetes, originally developed by Google, is an open-source solution, which rapidly became a standard for cloud solutions and containerized applications³. Using Kubernetes facilitates the deployment of microservice architectures⁴ and the management of microservice-based applications (applications composed of multiple components).

Kubernetes orchestrates Open Container Initiative compliant containers, including but not limited to Docker-based images. Docker is used to create and run containers, and Kubernetes orchestrates these containers.

Kubernetes' capabilities and services are numerous. The most important include:

- automatic scaling and deployment of applications to the cluster
- self-healing - monitors application performance and automatically launches and restarts if necessary
- automatic load-balancing of traffic between application instances
- enables automatic deployment of new application versions without stopping the service
- optimizes resource utilization: CPU, GPU, and memory
- automatic rollbacks, service discovery, and declarative desired-state configuration.

Kubernetes can be considered one of the most popular and stable technologies in the cloud infrastructure area, which is why it was chosen as the leading technology in the context of managing applications developed in the LUMEN project.

² <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/>

³ Sayfran, G., *Mastering Kubernetes: Level up your container orchestration skills with Kubernetes to build, run, secure, and observe large-scale distributed apps*, Packt Publishing, 2020.

⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microservices>

1.1.3 Containers

Containers, according to the Kubernetes documentation, are

‘technology for packaging an application along with its runtime dependencies’⁵.

A container is therefore an application packaged in a “box” that should run anywhere in a Docker environment. Docker, on the other hand,

‘is an open platform for developing, shipping, and running applications’⁶.

One of Docker's biggest advantages is the ability to separate applications from infrastructure. Along with the application, the mentioned “box” also contains all the dependencies needed to run the application.

1.2 The advantages of cloud solutions over the traditional infrastructure

Implementing a cloud infrastructure in the project should naturally support the use of various cloud solutions to address the specific needs of the project. A key example of the value added is the adaptation of GoTriple platform to cloud technology requirements just before being migrated to PCSS servers to support scalability and ease of management of the platform. More information about adapting the GoTriple platform is described in section 3.1.3.

The most important element of this technological upgrade of the GoTriple platform is the final ability to work with Kubernetes Container Orchestrator⁷ (more on Kubernetes in section 1.1.2). Kubernetes provides significantly improved scalability, flexibility, and performance, including rapid application deployments and improved management through process automation (more on the need for automation in sections 1.5.2 and 1.5.3).

Moreover, cloud solutions are more efficient when compared to the traditional infrastructure model composed of physical and virtual machines. Traditional bare-metal or VM-based environments often require manual scaling and fixed instance sizing, making them less elastic than cloud-native orchestration. Physical servers require continuous manual scaling. Virtual machines must always be managed for fixed-size instances. On the contrary, cloud solutions, such as Kubernetes, automate scaling and

⁵ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/containers/>

⁶ <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/docker-overview/>

⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/>

deployment and allow for dynamic resource sharing between projects. The system can therefore automatically adapt to changes in the environment.

Cloud solutions are therefore faster and more cost-effective compared to traditional infrastructures.

Referring to section 1.1, it is worth recalling that cloud infrastructure has given rise to new IT areas, such as DevOps, which have permanently changed the approach to working with software and services. DevOps is a combination of two English words: Development and Operations. The term originated in the first decade of the 21st century and refers to the culture of work between developers and teams responsible for infrastructure operations. Collaboration in these two areas brings technological benefits (fast, secure, and efficient operation of deployed applications) and business benefits (effective monitoring helps avoid potential problems)⁸.

Before the rise of DevOps, developers struggled with issues such as manual code review before deployment, manual code deployment, manual security testing, and manual problem resolution throughout the application lifecycle⁹. DevOps, through the development and use of automation tools such as Continuous Integration/Continuous Development (one of the most important practices in this work culture), has eliminated all of these time consuming manual tasks. Cloud infrastructure and the use of cloud-based technology solutions ensure work is conducted in accordance with best software development practices.

1.3 The key features of cloud infrastructure at a general level

Cloud infrastructure has several key features that make it a robust solution. These characteristics are often cited when explaining the benefits of this technological proposition.

1.3.1 Scalability

Scalability can be understood as adapting an application (or infrastructure) to changing requirements in a dynamic environment. Examples include the need for more memory (see section 3.2.3) or an increased number of users (see section 3.2.2).

In cloud infrastructure, scaling an application or a given component is an extremely fast process. Scaling can be performed either through the Platform as a Service (PaaS)

⁸ Krief, M., *Learning DevOps: A comprehensive guide to accelerating DevOps culture adoption with Terraform, Azure DevOps, Kubernetes, and Jenkins*, Packt Publishing, 2022.

⁹ Cowell, C., Lotz, N., Timberlake, C., *Automating DevOps with GitLab CI/CD Pipelines: Build efficient CI/CD pipelines to verify, secure, and deploy your code using real-life examples*, Packt Publishing, 2023.

dashboard (more on PaaS in section 1.4.3) or by updating the deployment configuration (e.g., the number of replicas) in a configuration file (see section 3.1.4). The use of these configuration files eliminates the need to create and configure physical or virtual machines manually.

It is worth noting that scalability works both ways (up and down). Applications can be sized to meet specific needs. Therefore, there's no need to maintain multiple virtual machines if application traffic is low.

Scalability can be automated. If high demand (like network traffic or not enough computation power) is detected, the application can automatically scale up.

1.3.2 Operation Management and continuity of Service

Applications can be deployed across multiple nodes depending on the replica configuration, so if one goes down, the application's lifecycle is not interrupted. The application continues to run freely on other virtual machine instances.

If an application were to run on only one node, this would not pose a problem in the context of cloud infrastructure. If that node fails, Kubernetes would spin up another node and launch the application on the new, working node.

1.3.3 Security

This section will highlight selected important aspects of application security. Section 3.1.4 discusses security in cloud infrastructure in more detail.

Containers (discussed in section 1.1.3) provide application-level isolation (namespaces, cgroups), reducing the impact of faults across components (see section 2.2.3), which effectively reduces the failure rate of individual applications. This isolation ensures that security issues affecting one application (enclosed in a container) should not impact the security of other applications.

Maintaining the security of infrastructure—physical machines and operating systems—relies on infrastructure administrators, not developers. This division of labor increases efficiency, especially in application implementation. Developers (the owners of applications running on PaaS) do not have to worry about security issues. The emphasis is therefore on technological innovation.

It is also not allowed to run the application with root privileges, which is related to the security of a given Pod in Kubernetes (more about Pods in section 2.2.2).

The aspects mentioned here are only selected examples.

1.3.4 Flexibility

Kubernetes, in particular, offers significant flexibility, allowing applications to run across a variety of environments. Kubernetes's architecture is modular and easily extensible, which positively impacts technological solutions such as ease of integration with various storage, ease of operation across various networks, and connection to various application monitoring systems.

Kubernetes provides a high level of flexibility by enabling applications to run consistently across various environments, including on-premise, cloud, and hybrid infrastructures. Its modular and extensible architecture allows easy integration with different storage, networking, and monitoring solutions. Through declarative configuration and automated management features, Kubernetes simplifies scaling, updating, and maintaining applications, making it adaptable to a wide range of workloads and organizational needs.

Flexibility also involves automated application management, which results in convenience in scaling, updating and maintaining applications.

1.4 Service models for infrastructures

The traditional service delivery model (service model) for infrastructure is called on-site service. The development of cloud infrastructures allowed the creation of three additional service models: Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS).

1.4.1 On-site

The on-site model is nothing more than the physical infrastructure, i.e., computers that constitute entire data centers at the chosen organisation either academic (e.g. universities, data and computing centers,...) or even businesses. The organisation therefore oversees the entire infrastructure—it has full control over the management of the physical infrastructure (i.e. electricity consumption, cooling, management of server racks,... maintenance), but pays the highest costs compared to other models.

1.4.2 Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)

In the IaaS model, the service provider owns the physical infrastructure but provides the client with cloud-based operating systems, applications, etc. Organizations with IT infrastructure can become a customer renting infrastructure services. So that each organisation controls its virtual IT assets, but not their physical backend.

1.4.3 Platform as a Service (PaaS)

The PaaS model goes a step further than IaaS. In PaaS, the provider offers a development platform, along with the tools (software) needed to create, deploy, and manage applications. The provider controls the physical and virtual machines, while the client manages application code, containerisation, runtime configuration and data life cycle (see section 1.1).

Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PCSS) offers the PaaS infrastructure for the LUMEN project. In the following parts of the document this service model will be referred to as **PCSS PaaS**.

1.4.4 Software as a Service (SaaS)

SaaS delivers fully managed applications accessible through a browser or API, with no infrastructure management required from the user. This software is available, for example, in web browsers. In this case, the provider owns the entire infrastructure and hosts the application intended for external users. It is responsible for guaranteeing the continuity of service while the service provider is responsible for the development and maintenance of the service offered to customers.

1.5 Operational methodologies

Within cloud infrastructure, several methodological approaches can be distinguished. This section focuses only on those directly applied within LUMEN. For example, there are application deployment methodologies or service deployment methodologies (an example would be PaaS, described in more detail in section 1.4.3). Methodologies in the context of cloud infrastructure can also have an operational nature, referring to the way the infrastructure is managed. The following sections describe key concepts in this context and concern the infrastructure operational methodologies used within the PCSS PaaS infrastructure in the LUMEN project.

1.5.1 Infrastructure as Code

Infrastructure as Code (IaC) treats infrastructure configuration the same way as software code. This approach emphasizes repeatable procedures to implement changes¹⁰.

Using IaC practices brings numerous benefits, including the safe and rapid implementation of changes to infrastructure, the development of common practices at the interface between two disciplines (strengthening collaboration between developers and operations teams), business profitability, and the effective elimination of potential problems¹¹.

IaC addresses the core challenge of making frequent changes without compromising stability. On the one hand, introducing modification can lead to failure. On the other, without modification, proper development is impossible.

However, IaC benefits greatly from the agility offered by cloud infrastructure (therefore, the IaC practice fits perfectly with the PCSS PaaS infrastructure). The speed of change implementation is seen as a positive aspect in IaC practice. This is primarily because IaC defines everything as code, creates small and modifiable components, and ensures continuous testing¹².

IaC, as observed, brings benefits not only between the developer and the infrastructure operations team, but also in the relationship between developers and testers. This collaboration model is fully aligned with how LUMEN distributes operational responsibilities across partners.

Moving away from traditional infrastructure practices related to physical infrastructure in favor of new, tailored to the needs of cloud infrastructure forces a new way of thinking about infrastructure, and consequently - new methods of working with software, i.e. IaC¹³.

1.5.2 GitOps

¹⁰ Morris, K., *Infrastructure as Code: Managing Servers in the Cloud*, O'Reilly Media, 2016.

¹¹ Morris, K., *Infrastructure as Code: Managing Servers in the Cloud*, O'Reilly Media, 2016.

¹² Krief, M., *Learning DevOps: A comprehensive guide to accelerating DevOps culture adoption with Terraform, Azure DevOps, Kubernetes, and Jenkins*, Packt Publishing, 2022.

¹³ Arundel, J., Domingus, J., *Cloud Native DevOps with Kubernetes: Building, Deploying, and Scaling Modern Applications in the Cloud*, O'Reilly Media, 2019.

To understand the origins of GitOps, it's important to recall the term DevOps. DevOps is a combination of two English words: Development and Operations. The term originated in the first decade of the 21st century and refers to the culture of work between developers and teams responsible for infrastructure operations. Collaboration in these two areas brings technological benefits (fast, secure, and efficient operation of deployed applications) and business benefits (effective monitoring helps avoid potential problems)¹⁴.

The practice described in section 1.5.1 of Infrastructure as Code allows better DevOps development (automation, repeatable infrastructure deployment). The next section 1.5.3 describes CI/CD, one of the key elements enabling improved collaboration between developers (Dev) and infrastructure operations teams (Ops).

GitOps builds on Git¹⁵ as the central source of truth for infrastructure. It is also a code-working practice that can be situated within Infrastructure as Code and the DevOps culture. It primarily relies on treating Git as a single source of truth. Git enables collaborative work between several people, including validating and checking the work of other developers. The potential for rapid testing of infrastructure changes is one of the key advantages of GitOps practices.

Infrastructure changes are therefore handled similarly to code—they are automated, versioned, and verified by the Git version control system. Process automation is linked to the term CI/CD, discussed in section 1.5.3.

1.5.3 Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment

The acronyms CI and CD refer to Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Deployment (CD) processes. These processes play a significant role in the context of deploying applications to the production Kubernetes environment. These processes positively influence the phenomenon of automation at the global level of application deployment, i.e., from writing code to deploying that code in the production environment.

Continuous integration(CI) is about the continuous process of integrating code with a repository managed by the Git version control system. One of the key principles here is the approach of frequently integrating smaller batches of code. It's considered bad practice to integrate larger changes sporadically. Smaller components are much easier to test. Testability, in turn, is an integral part of the CI process. Tests can be

¹⁴ Krief, M., *Learning DevOps: A comprehensive guide to accelerating DevOps culture adoption with Terraform, Azure DevOps, Kubernetes, and Jenkins*, Packt Publishing, 2022.

¹⁵ <https://git-scm.com/>

implemented, for example, with tools like Jenkins (one of the most popular automation process management tools designed to work with CI/CD).

CD happens after CI and pushes validated changes to production automatically. A poorly planned CI process will negatively impact the final result in the production environment (the CD process will then fail to achieve its intended goals). With well-organized CI, CD will deploy changes to the application in the production environment. The immutability of the container image comes into play here (discussed in section 2.2.3), which allows for consistent library versioning (differences between versions of individual dependencies in the development and production environments have been a common cause of application failures). The most important continuous deployment strategies include delivering updates (an inherent Kubernetes mechanism that does not stop the running application during upgrades) or blue-green deployments (the idea is to intensify control when deploying applications to new environments)¹⁶.

The implementation of CI/CD processes also affects the security of managed applications and is considered one of the determinants of the Security by Design methodology.

1.5.4 Security by Design

The Security by Design methodology in the context of PaaS primarily focuses on a conceptual approach to application design. The security of all services within the entire PCSS PaaS infrastructure is not treated as a supplementary element or an additional feature that would distinguish the infrastructure from others. Security in PCSS PaaS is inherent and implemented from the very beginning at every step of infrastructure evolution.

Security design in LUMEN is implemented at a global level, being an integral part of both the physical infrastructure and the code deployment process (as well as many other elements that could be described in the context of deploying a cloud infrastructure).

This approach aims to eliminate potential security problems as efficiently and effectively as possible by anticipating them. In summary, the goal is to protect against security issues as broadly as possible, rather than reacting only when they actually occur.

A secure environment can also be created in Kubernetes using the technology's various APIs. This is particularly relevant for LUMEN services that require isolated or restricted execution environments. Each case of creating an environment for a new application

¹⁶ Burns B., Villalba E., Strelbel D., Evenson L., *Best practices in Kubernetes. How to build successful applications*, O'Reilly Media, 2019.

should be considered individually. Kubernetes offers a lot of security solutions, which does not mean that it is mandatory to use all of them at once (this would probably be almost impossible). Therefore, security considerations must be carefully considered and tailored to the actual needs of a given application runtime environment. In Kubernetes, you can secure Pods or images, apply security in the form of roles and user access to individual services, and implement various network policies¹⁷.

Other examples of implementing Security by Design in PCSS PaaS have already been explored and are discussed in other sections.

This includes a structured user permissions control system (mentioned in section 2.2.3, role-based access control (RBAC)) or advanced application monitoring systems (discussed in section 2.2.5).

The previous section, 1.5.3, referenced the important CI/CD process, which impacts code version control security.

One of the sections (specifically, section 3.1.9, titled "Security Assessment") describing the migration of the GoTriple platform includes a pre-defined plan for establishing security rules for the migrated application – this is also an example of implementing the Security by Design methodology. This illustrates how security planning is integrated into operational workflows before deployment.

1.6 Deployment models

In addition to the cloud service models described above (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS), cloud infrastructures are typically classified according to their deployment model. Deployment models describe *where* the cloud infrastructure is hosted and *who* controls it.

1.6.1 Public Cloud

A public cloud is operated by a commercial provider (e.g., AWS, Azure, Google Cloud). Resources are shared across multiple clients, billed on demand, and highly elastic. Public clouds offer convenience and rapid provisioning, but users have limited control over the underlying infrastructure.

1.6.2 Private Cloud

¹⁷ Burns B., Beda J., Hightower K., Evenson L., *Kubernetes: Up & Running. Dive into the Future of Infrastructure*, O'Reilly Media, 2022.

A private cloud is dedicated to a single organisation or consortium. It provides cloud capabilities (scalability, automation, container orchestration, etc.) but runs on infrastructure fully controlled by the organisation or its partners. Private clouds are typically chosen when stronger governance, data protection, or customisation requirements apply. The PCSS PaaS infrastructure used in LUMEN falls into this category.

1.6.3 Hybrid Cloud

A hybrid cloud combines private cloud infrastructure with public cloud services. It enables organisations to keep sensitive workloads on private infrastructure while using public cloud elasticity when needed. Hybrid setups are increasingly adopted for AI workloads, backup strategies, or burst capacity.

2. Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PCSS) Platform as a Service (PaaS)

2.1 Basic outline

Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PCSS) introduced its PaaS offering in 2019 (described in section 1.4.3), and it is now used across all divisions and most departments. It runs on top of the two physical data centers, handles 800+ domain names, thousands of containers, and is maintained and developed by hundreds of software engineers. PaaS is used for both commercial and public projects. The solution is therefore well tested and stabilized at PCSS.

One of the most important aspects of PaaS is the elimination of infrastructure-level responsibilities. When using PaaS, responsibilities related solely to applications and data should be considered for the user. Challenges such as the underlying runtime environment, operating system, and virtual machines are fully abstracted away. PaaS therefore provides greater flexibility and operational freedom, while eliminating a number of areas where infrastructure failures could occur.

Using PaaS on the PCSS infrastructure is highly efficient thanks to the extensive support system. Additional assistance is provided by the advanced user support system – the PCSS PaaS service desk. This support provides, for example, information about failures, new installations or updates. Support and automation features significantly improve operational reliability and project management.

These are the most important features of PCSS PaaS:

- Container orchestration
- Dynamic provisioning of different types of storage for containers
- Container image registries
- Automatic HTTPS certificates
- Automatic health checks and notifications
- Custom monitoring and alerting
- Log aggregation
- Automatic backups
- Access control on URL/IP
- Data center failover
- Access to GPU processing power

Together, these capabilities provide a complete operational environment for deploying, monitoring, and scaling services.

Each of these functionalities will be described in the next section 2.2.

2.2 Key components of PCSS PaaS

All functionalities are described in general terms, providing a basic overview of the PCSS PaaS infrastructure. Selected elements demonstrate good practices for implementing and managing projects on the PCSS infrastructure. Therefore, this chapter should be treated as a background for the cloud infrastructure plan in the LUMEN project.

2.2.1 Container orchestration, based on OKD, which is the upstream of RedHat OpenShift and an extension of Kubernetes

OKD, the open-source upstream of Red Hat OpenShift (Kubernetes-based container application platform developed by Red Hat, which is the paid version of OKD)¹⁸, provides a Kubernetes distribution with additional enterprise-grade capabilities, such as:

- manual/auto scaling: allows for up-scale and/or down-scale of the services without effort, either by manual intervention or some automatic routines,
- self-healing: Kubernetes detects and fixes errors independently, ensuring the uninterrupted and correct operation of all applications,
- metrics collection: for example, observing the performance or resource use of the container,
- log aggregation: can be done in many different configurations and patterns,
- multitenancy: orchestration used to run multiple isolated workloads (for different users, teams, or applications) on a single shared infrastructure, which increases efficiency and reduces costs,
- security by design (methodology discussed in more detail in section 3.1.4).

2.2.2 Dynamic provisioning of different types of storage for containers

A Pod in OKD is the smallest deployable unit and may consist of one or more containers, it is a set of running containers in a given cluster¹⁹. A cluster can be defined as a unit for working with individual containers²⁰.

¹⁸ <https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/cloud-computing/openshift>

¹⁹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/containers/images/>

²⁰ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/architecture/>

Volume storage in OKD is therefore closely related to Pods. Volume management is also an important element for PCSS PaaS and primarily refers to the ability to store and expand volume resources.

OKD has several volume access modes that are used for various use cases related to storing data on a given cluster. Volume access modes therefore ensure customer needs in the context of applications that vary in complexity or complexity.

According to OKD documentation:

'OKD uses the Kubernetes persistent volume (PV) framework to allow cluster administrators to provision persistent storage for a cluster. Developers can use persistent volume claims (PVCs) to request PV resources without having specific knowledge of the underlying storage infrastructure'²¹.

The concept of PV is related to the concept of storage class, which indicates an appropriately defined resource according to criteria such as performance or availability.

Depending on the OKD cluster, there are different numbers of storage classes in PCSS PaaS that can be used by Pods and whose volumes can be accessed through the defined (mentioned above) volume access modes.

Storage classes are regularly monitored by PCSS, particularly in terms of performance and potential functional issues. Therefore, infrastructure users can report potential issues via the service desk or consult the "Known Issues" database, which describes the most important failure cases.

The capacity of a given storage class can be easily increased depending on needs. This elasticity avoids service downtime during storage expansion. However, it is important to maintain a reasonable size. This is essential because reasonably sized volumes are much easier to administer. In specific cases, such as migration (see the section 3.1 on GoTriple migration), a reasonable volume size actually simplifies the entire process (oversized overheads slow down performance and are more difficult to manage).

2.2.3 Container image registries

A container registry, or simply registry, is a service primarily used for storing container images.

²¹ <https://docs.okd.io/latest/storage/understanding-persistent-storage.html>

According to the Docker documentation, a container image is a kind of packaging that contains all the files, libraries, and configurations necessary to run an application. A container image has two key principles. The first is immutability, meaning that a previously created image cannot be modified. The second is layering, where a single layer reflects a set of system changes (these can be added, removed, or modified)²².

The same documentation also explains the concept of a registry:

‘while you’re working with registries, you might hear the terms registry and repository as if they’re interchangeable. Even though they’re related, they’re not quite the same thing’²³.

A registry is a centralized location used to store and share container images²⁴. Registries are divided into public and private.

The Kubernetes documentation also provides valuable insight into this topic²⁵. Container images are pushed to a given registry before being referenced by a specific Pod.

PCSS has its own registry for container images; it is private and accessible only within networks managed by PCSS. It also allows for so-called robot accounts (accounts for applications is PaaS registry).

The PCSS PaaS registry fully supports Docker-compatible container images. Images can be pushed, pulled (it is organized around role-based access control (RBAC), which

“is a method of regulating access to computer or network resources based on the roles of individual users within your organization”²⁶,

stored, scanned, and managed. This private registry allows for logical separation of applications, teams, and environments while enforcing granular access policies. It also operates as a proxy to Docker Hub, enabling transparent caching of public images and eliminating issues related to Docker Hub’s rate limits.

²² <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/docker-concepts/the-basics/what-is-an-image/>

²³ <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/docker-concepts/the-basics/what-is-a-registry/>

²⁴ Registry is often confused with repository, which is a terminological error. A repository should be considered as a collection of related container images within a given registry. Registry is therefore a superordinate concept to repository. See more:

<https://docs.docker.com/get-started/docker-concepts/the-basics/what-is-a-registry/>

²⁵ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/containers/images/>

²⁶ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/access-authn-authz/rbac/>

2.2.4 Automatic HTTPS certificates

PCSS PaaS offers automated HTTPS (a secure version of the http protocol, which is primarily used to encrypt data between the client (browser) and the website) certificate deployment using Let's Encrypt²⁷ and cert-manager. This ensures that applications deployed on PaaS are always served securely without manual certificate handling. Even if the user sends a non-encrypted request, it will be automatically redirected to an encrypted request. This mechanism is configurable - the administrator/application owner can therefore disable automatic redirection.

Before discussing the HTTPS protocol certification process, it is necessary to recall the definition of the term route according to OKD:

'A route allows you to host your application at a public URL. It can either be secure or unsecured, depending on the network security configuration of your application'²⁸.

For default routes in the application, there's no need to generate a certificate – they already have a wildcard certificate implemented, securing all associated routes by default. PCSS PaaS users can find a detailed description of the HTTPS certificate generation process in the appropriate (internal at PCSS) documentation (available for review by developers working on the PCSS infrastructure).

On the one hand, the cert-manager in PCSS PaaS allows you to use basic certification automation functionalities, such as creating a certificate or adding a certificate to a selected route. On the other hand, there is also the option of using additional features, such as adding decoded certificates' information or an expiry alerts service (helpful when automatic certificate renewal is not enabled).

2.2.5 Automatic health checks and notifications, custom monitoring and alerting, log aggregation

Within PCSS PaaS it is also possible to automatically check an application's health via routes. By adding the appropriate annotation to the route, you can add a given application to the monitoring service. Route annotations are divided into required and

²⁷ <https://letsencrypt.org/>

²⁸ <https://docs.okd.io/4.13/networking/routes/route-configuration.html>

optional annotations. The choice of annotation, i.e., the appropriate route description, influences the subsequent communication process between the PCSS PaaS user and the appropriate monitoring service. Communication with the monitoring service is based on previously established roles within a given project. For example, an admin or editor user will be able to receive notifications from the monitoring system.

Metrics in PaaS are numerical data that can be collected automatically. Some of this data is collected by default, the rest remains optional. This data allows you to better understand the current state of the infrastructure.

Alerts, in turn, are automatically generated information that comes to the administrator and allows detecting problems at an early stage (for example in the context of metrics exceeding the threshold of the norm).

To modify metrics and alerts, the user must have the administrator role. This ensures that only authorised maintainers can adjust monitoring rules for dedicated services. If the user does not have the administrator role but wants to modify metrics and alerts, they must be granted special permissions in the project, such as monitoring-edit, monitoring-rules-edit, or alert-routing-edit.

In OKD, the metrics reporting process is performed using objects. The most important ones used in PCSS PaaS include ServiceMonitors²⁹ (e.g. PodMonitors³⁰), PrometheusRules³¹, and AlertManagerConfigs³².

These objects are used for various types of notifications and alerts. For example, with Prometheus support, PCSS PaaS users can deploy their own common alerts and configure email notifications for common issues within a given project. This type of monitoring, based on Prometheus³³, operates on the same infrastructure and is helpful in inspecting processes such as workload or in-app errors.

One way to deploy your common alerts is to deploy a helm chart. According to OKD, helm is a

‘software package manager that simplifies the deployment of applications and services to OKD clusters’³⁴.

²⁹ https://docs.okd.io/latest/rest_api/monitoring_apis/servicemonitor-monitoring-coreos-com-v1.html

³⁰ https://docs.okd.io/latest/rest_api/monitoring_apis/podmonitor-monitoring-coreos-com-v1.html

³¹ https://docs.okd.io/latest/rest_api/monitoring_apis/prometheusrule-monitoring-coreos-com-v1.html

³²

<https://docs.okd.io/4.18/observability/monitoring/configuring-user-workload-monitoring/configuring-alerts-and-notifications-uwm.html>

³³ Prometheus’ website:

<https://prometheus.io/>

More about Prometheus in the OKD documentation:

<https://docs.okd.io/4.13/virt/support/monitoring/virt-prometheus-queries.html>

³⁴ https://docs.okd.io/latest/applications/working_with_helm_charts/understanding-helm.html

The helm packaging format is called charts. A chart is a collection of files that provide metadescriptive information about OKD resources. In PCSS PaaS, helm chart allows, by default, the definition of alerts for issues such as:

- Container stuck
- High CPU usage
- High memory usage
- Init container stuck
- PVC Stuck
- Persistent volume filling up
- Pod unknown or terminating
- Container repeated restarts (includes OOM)
- Pod Disruption Budget at limit

The PCSS PaaS infrastructure recognizes that alerts for the aforementioned issues should cover the most common problems in the project. It is also possible to expand the notification system and customize alerts to meet additional needs. For this purpose, users will find specifically described procedures in the PCSS PaaS documentation, which will allow for efficient and effective customization of the alert and notification system.

A log is a time-based record of events in a given project. Logs in OKD are an essential element of monitoring a given application or project.

The log aggregation system in OKD (version 4) is implemented via LokiStack³⁵. Log aggregation is accessible directly from the OKD interface in the 'Aggregated Logs' console. By default, logs are retained for 5 days for experimental projects and 14 days for production projects.

The project administrator can always submit a request to change the limits via the ticket system on the PCSS PaaS infrastructure.

2.2.6 Automatic backups

All objects existing in individual applications and projects are backed up in PCSS PaaS.

However, volumes, understood as volume under a PVC (see section number 2.2.2), must meet several conditions to be backed up.

The first requirement is that the PVC must be mounted to at least one running Pod. This Pod, in turn, must be appropriately annotated. The annotation must include the name of

³⁵ https://docs.okd.io/4.15/observability/logging/log_storage/cluster-logging-loki.html

the volumes to be backed up. It is also possible to back up multiple volumes to the same Pod.

Currently, only the administrator can manage backups and the process of restoring projects and volume data. Backups are performed according to defined schedules. This ensures controlled and secure handling of backup and restore operation.

2.2.7 Networking and access control on URL/IP

Each project network (it is a logical computer network in a given project, which is isolated from networks in other projects on a given cluster) in PCSS PaaS is separated, and all communication within the project is unrestricted by default. Each project is accessible through a default router.

However, applications can be exposed to the outside world using routes. The route concept was presented earlier in section 2.2.4. Routes support the HTTPS protocol, but are also compatible with the standard Transport Layer Security (TLS) – cryptographic protocol for network communication.

Each cluster in the PCSS PaaS has a default domain that can be used by all projects and which is protected by a certificate (it is possible to use this certificate for free and communicate via https). Therefore, the user does not need to configure Domain Name Service (DNS).

Creating a custom domain is entirely possible, but one condition must be met. The domain must refer to a specific cluster in DNS (it can be requested through the ticket system in the PCSS infrastructure).

Projects in PCSS PaaS can, however, communicate with each other. For inter-project communication, one of the OKD resources, the NetworkPolicy object, must be defined. Creating and modifying a NetworkPolicy object allows the administrator user to set customized access policies.

To increase project security, each new project receives default access policies (otherwise, the newly created project would remain completely open). These default policies are available from several places, e.g. VPN PCSS, wired network with certificate or Internal Cluster IP addresses. It is recommended to leave the default access policies. It is advised only to add new NetworkPolicy objects if needed to allow other projects to communicate with specific services.

2.2.8 Data center failover

This refers to a static error page that displays when an application is unavailable.

The page is dedicated to a given application (it can be customized) and must be prepared in advance. It's worth noting that the page is hosted in a different data center.

In terms of page preparation, this should be done using basic front-end technologies, such as HTML, Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), and JavaScript (JS).

The page will be displayed in cases such as:

- the application raises errors
- cannot receive HTTP responses from the application
- the infrastructure or the entire data center is down

2.2.9 GPU and its presence on PCSS PaaS

A Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) is responsible for rendering images or animations. A GPU can perform multiple operations simultaneously. This multitasking capability distinguishes a GPU from a Central Processing Unit (CPU).

The GPU is ideally suited for working with Large Language Models (LLMs) thanks to its ability to perform simultaneous tasks. As an example, it is worth mentioning one of the key aspects of LLMs' operation: training language models. GPU multitasking significantly accelerates the training process. Clusters on the PCSS PaaS infrastructure have GPUs connected to them (individual Pods on a given cluster may contain GPU slices), which can be used for LLM-related tasks.

2.3 OKD Clusters at PCSS

Clusters are pooled computer nodes that manage containers³⁶. Each cluster is placed in a specific region. In OKD, a region is the physical infrastructure space where data centers are located. The choice of region affects the cluster's subsequent availability and performance.

There are currently five OKD clusters on the PCSS PaaS infrastructure. The clusters are accessible from various networks. The clusters' existence is determined by various

³⁶ More about clusters in the kubernetes documentation:
<https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/architecture/>

purposes, such as testing, development, and strictly experimental, as well as production or development-production.

Each cluster has its own URL and IP address and can be based on different OKD versions.

For the LUMEN project, a cluster based on OKD 4.19 was selected. This version provides long-term stability and GPU support required for advanced LUMEN services. This cluster is available for both development and production purposes. The selected service also offers GPU expansion (see section 2.2.9), which is important for further application development in the LUMEN project. The cluster described here also proves to be the default choice for projects in the PCSS PaaS. LUMEN thus received a service from PCSS that is well-established in the infrastructure environment.

3. PCSS PaaS as an infrastructure practice at LUMEN

The main goal of this section is to outline how the functionalities specific to the PCSS PaaS infrastructure (discussed in section 2) and selected assumptions of the cloud infrastructure (presented in section 1) are applied in practice in the LUMEN project. The section can therefore be treated as of how the infrastructure plan is practically implemented for LUMEN.

3.1 GoTriple migration as proof of concept for cloud infrastructure at LUMEN

This section describes the process of migrating the GoTriple platform (dedicated to the field of Social Sciences and Humanities) to the PCSS PaaS infrastructure.

3.1.1 GoTriple migration - global overview

As part of the LUMEN project, the migration of the GoTriple platform to the PaaS infrastructure at PCSS was arranged and carried out (the advantages of this technological solution are discussed in more detail in section 2). The platform is a dedicated solution for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) researchers and also forms the technological heart of the LUMEN project (GoTriple serves as a starting point for the White Label Platform being developed for other scientific disciplines) and that is why the migration of GoTriple was chosen as a proof of concept to test the infrastructural capabilities of PCSS).

Four European institutions involved in the LUMEN project worked on the migration process: Net7, OPERAS, Foxcub, and PCSS. This distribution of roles mirrors the operational model used in other LUMEN components. OPERAS and Foxcub were primarily responsible for providing specifications for the individual components to be migrated. These institutions also actively assisted in conceptualizing the migration. Net7 and PCSS were responsible for the implementation. In close collaboration, developers from these institutions completed all migration-related tasks. The tasks related to the discussed migration were carried out within Work Package 4 (Task 4.2) and Work Package 5 (Task 5.2). This cooperation is an example of efficient communication between individual Work Packages and awareness of the global perspective on the LUMEN project.

From the onset, the GoTriple platform migration was treated as a proof of concept for the infrastructure implementation at LUMEN. It validated both technical feasibility and

inter-partner workflows. The migration process, thoroughly analyzed step-by-step by the participating institutions, served as a practical implementation for the initial cloud infrastructure plan.

The following sections detail the migration steps for the GoTriple platform. Similar work will be carried out later on other applications built in LUMEN.

3.1.2 Access to PCSS infrastructure

The first stage of Net7 and PCSS's collaboration on the GoTriple platform migration was to enable Net7 developers to work on the PCSS infrastructure. Invitations to the infrastructure followed a strictly defined process. This process includes identity management, VPN configuration, and OKD project-level role assignment. Therefore, in June 2025, a special webinar led by infrastructure specialists at PCSS was organized. On the one hand, webinar participants had the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the theoretical aspects of the PCSS infrastructure, both in the context of PaaS and Virtual Machines. On the other hand, a practical step-by-step path to accessing the PCSS infrastructure was presented.

Two key elements of access to the PCSS infrastructure are the configuration of LDAP accounts and VPN networks. Net7 was the first beneficiary of this solution.

A single account within the VPN network has currently been configured. In the future, there will be a need to have additional users to allow other developers access to the PCSS infrastructure. The experience gained in this initial phase will therefore allow for seamless connection of other developers, depending on the implementation needs of the project.

In parallel to the account configuration process by external developers, a space for the LUMEN project was also created on the OKD instance by PaaS administrators at PCSS. The project was created with default input parameters (requesting administrators to set appropriate quotas), such as CPU limit, memory limit, and storage. As mentioned, this is an OKD (Kubernetes technology) instance, so it has all the beneficial features (initially defined by default) described in section 2. These quotas can be expanded once service load is characterised.

After configuring the accounts for the PCSS infrastructure, it was possible to add the Net7 developer account to the LUMEN project on OKD. The Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) account is compatible with the OKD cluster, which hosts the LUMEN project's storage. The user for the LUMEN project was granted appropriate permissions based on their role in the project. Assigning permissions is closely tied to Kubernetes' role-based access control (RBAC), which was mentioned in section 2.2.3 regarding container orchestration. This person and their role (in this case, the administrator) were role-bound to the LUMEN project.

3.1.3 GoTriple adjustment

The migration process actually began with a technological assessment of the GoTriple platform. Diagnosing the issues allowed the development of technical solutions, which were immediately implemented in practice. Net7 and PCSS developers worked on the assessment.

The GoTriple platform had its own Docker image, and its presence proved to be a positive assumption (an image is crucial in the context of working with containers in general – more on this in section 2.2.3). However, any actions on a given Docker image were impossible due to library versioning issues. As it turned out, the GoTriple platform had a slightly older version of Java, which was efficiently upgraded to a higher version, compatible with Kubernetes requirements.

The next step was to adjust the paths in the Dockerfile, as they were leading to incorrect configuration files. Furthermore, the configuration files were embedded in the Dockerfile, which is generally not a good practice. Both the path and configuration file issues were urgently addressed.

Later, the `-Xms` and `-Xmx` parameters were also established for Java application. This ensured predictable memory allocation for Kubernetes scheduling. In the Docker file, these parameters refer to the initial and final memory sizes of the application, respectively. Careful management of these parameters has a significant impact on application optimization and performance.

There were also minor issues connecting to ElasticSearch from Mediator (a component application of the GoTriple platform). The problem was identified as the default client for ElasticSearch – Mediator was launching it automatically. Disabling this default client resolved the communication issues between Mediator and ElasticSearch.

Additionally, the Mediator application was creating files in the container itself in areas where it didn't actually have permission, which generated a 'Permission denied' access error. Therefore, the configuration needed to be changed to allow file writing to the specified volume.

After eliminating the problems described above, the GoTriple platform was considered to be finally adapted to the migration process to the PCSS infrastructure.

3.1.4 Creating Kubernetes objects

Once the GoTriple platform was adapted to the appropriate technological requirements for Kubernetes and the OKD instance, work on the actual migration phase could begin.

One of the fundamental steps then becomes the creation of Kubernetes objects. According to the Kubernetes documentation, objects can be defined as

'persistent entities in the Kubernetes system. Kubernetes uses these entities to represent the state of your cluster'³⁷.

Such objects typically specify what is being containerized, what resources a given application has, and how the application should behave (rules related to restarts or upgrades)³⁸.

Two of the key Kubernetes objects are Deployment and StatefulSet. Both objects are used to run a set of Pods, but StatefulSet additionally attaches a unique identity to each Pod. The main difference between these objects lies in the nature of the application's state. For stateful applications (applications that remember all user or client activities and record them, creating a user history), StatefulSet is definitely preferable. For stateless applications (applications that do not need to record user activity and function independently of user or client information), Deployment is a better alternative.

For the Mediator application, it has been decided to use the Deployment object, while for ELasticSearch, a StatefulSet would be used. It's worth noting that these objects can be replaced if needed, although this requires careful handling for stateful services.

Next, the remaining Kubernetes objects necessary for hosting were created. These include YAML files (files responsible for Kubernetes resources), ConfigMap (environment variables, not containing sensitive data), Secrets (containing sensitive data such as passwords), Services (allowing, for example, to share Deployments within the cluster), and Routes (more on these in section 2.2.4).

3.1.5 Docker images processing - Kubernetes-compliant Docker images

Net7, with the help from PCSS, converted the docker images for our services into kubernetes-ready images and deployments. This included adapting entrypoints, permissions, resource flags, and environment injection.

Some services (Elasticsearch, MariaDB and activeMQ (technology for exchanging messages between different applications³⁹)) were installed from their upstream images. Net7 provided the configuration and system requirements and PCSS configured them accordingly.

³⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/working-with-objects/>

³⁸ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/working-with-objects/>

³⁹ Applications can send messages to the queue stack, and other applications can receive those messages. The queue stack ensures message longevity – messages without a recipient remain in the stack, waiting to be received.

In the near future we are going to migrate more services to the PCSS infrastructure (as mentioned in section 4), following the procedure used for the already-migrated services.

3.1.6 Databases migration

One of the most important migrated components remains the database; in the case of the GoTriple platform, this is MariaDB (i.e., relational database management). Currently, MariaDB has been packaged in Deployment, but due to the application's stateful nature, it will most likely be switched to StatefulSet (as mentioned in section 3.1.4, the switch is not a technological challenge). This transition must ensure persistent volume continuity to avoid data regeneration. The MariaDB instance also has a Service (which will always be present) and its own Route (in this case, the technology consortium working on the GoTriple migration will certainly consider the validity of the Route). The MariaDB migration process has therefore passed the initial phase, which will be subject to a thorough re-evaluation in the future.

After the initial set-up of the MariaDB service, Net7 was able to create the required databases and migrate the data from the existing servers.

As part of the GoTriple platform, a component called Drupal was also created, for which there is also a database component, included in the migration process.

3.1.7 ElasticSearch migration

The fundamental component of the GoTriple platform is ElasticSearch (a variant of the search engine). ElasticSearch is a technology that allows for very fast searching and analysis of data sets⁴⁰. To migrate it, PCSS used a solution called Operator. This is a design pattern in Kubernetes. According to the documentation, Operators 'make use of custom resources to manage applications and their components'⁴¹. Operator is therefore closely linked to automation processes in Kubernetes.

In practice, Operator independently created StatefulSet (see section 3.1.4), then Services (also section 3.1.4) and Volumes (see section 2.2.2), and finally deployed the entire ElasticSearch.

⁴⁰ One of the features of ElasticSearch is data indexing, closely related to full-text search.

⁴¹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/extend-kubernetes/operator/>

In comparison, MariaDB only has a single database instance (ElasticSearch has multiple instances), so the manual process was generally less complex to perform. Furthermore, there could also be a potential issue with the availability of the appropriate Operator for the MariaDB application.

After the initial set-up of the elasticsearch service, Net7 ran some scripts to configure the mapping and settings of the required indices. Net7 also created the required stored scripts.

Afterwards, we used the “reindex” elasticsearch feature to migrate the data from the existing elasticsearch installation to the new one.

The reindex procedure presented us with some challenges, due to the existing service having some difficulties, but in the end we were able to copy all the data over to the new infrastructure.

3.1.8 Backups and snapshots

The PCSS PaaS infrastructure includes application backup functionality. This is described in more detail in section 2.2.6. In the context of the GoTriple platform, developers can design their own backup plans for individual platform components.

As an example of one such solution, we can cite MariaDB volume snapshots, which provide point-in-time copies of the underlying storage volume and can be scheduled at defined intervals.

Net7 developers have already proposed a preliminary backup plan.

GoTriple platform backup plan

Things to be backed up:

- DBMS to be backed up at least once a day
- Elasticsearch: regular dumps or snapshots (daily at least)

- SCRE⁴² Cache⁴³: the front-end indexes are not strictly necessary as they can be rebuilt from the cache
- ActiveMQ file system: to be backed up?
- MariaDB to be backed up at least once a day

Restore policy to be defined and tested.

Other aspects:

Logs:

- Technical logs (e.g. SCRE's after being gzipped) to be kept for 1-2 weeks
- Front-end logs: storage of gzipped logs for X months (to be verified).

The above plan should be considered a preliminary proposal, subject to change as current needs arise. However, the PCSS PaaS infrastructure allows for flexible adaptation in terms of both backups and application security rules.

3.1.9 Security assessment

The OKD Cluster infrastructure also offers numerous security options for hosted applications. A detailed security policy plan will be created for the migrated GoTriple platform. This plan will align with PCSS PaaS security guidelines and Kubernetes best practices. This will address issues such as:

- exposing (or not) the application to the outside world
- specifying the IP addresses that will be allowed to access specific services (whitelisting)
- creating an image repository for searching for vulnerabilities in images.

Net7 developers have already presented a preliminary outline of the security policies and needs for the GoTriple platform. The most important aspects of this plan are described below.

GoTriple platform security plan

⁴² SCRE (Semantic Content Retrieval Engine) is the whole pipeline that harvests and processes content from sources, and updates the Elasticsearch indexes used by the front-end of GoTriple. More on this topic in the second chapter of this document: De Santis L., Cau F., Giacomi D., Agosta T., Homo J., Ardizzone V., Lamata Martinez I., *TRIPLE Deliverable D4.4 Technical and User Documentation for the TRIPLE system*. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/7708784>.

⁴³ The SCRE Cache is a set of indexes used by SCRE for its processing. Basically when a record is imported (e.g. by querying an OAI-PMH endpoint) the various processing steps end by updating its instance on the SCRE Cache. Then a particular service, called Publisher, fetches data in the SCRE Cache for populating the front-end indexes.

The SCRE mediator⁴⁴ service needs to interact with three services:

- The management backend (a Drupal application, yet to be migrated to PCSS infrastructure)
- The frontend APIs (a Laravel application, yet to be migrated to PCSS infrastructure)
- An external translation service of which we cannot predict the IP address

Because of the latter we cannot block access to the SCRE mediator based on IPs or other means as it needs to be accessed by at least one external service. Alternatives such as token-based access or mTLS should be evaluated since IP-based filtering is impossible.

The elasticsearch cluster will only be accessed by two services:

- The SCRE mediator
- The frontend APIs (a Laravel application, yet to be migrated to PCSS infrastructure)

Once the frontend APIs are migrated to the PCSS infrastructure, we could limit the access to the elasticsearch cluster to only those two services/IPs/Pods.

The Drupal application and the frontend APIs will be accessed from everywhere, and therefore their access must be public.

The database service is only accessed by other Pods from within the infrastructure itself and can be secured accordingly.

The activeMQ service is also only accessed by other Pods from within the infrastructure itself and can be secured accordingly.

3.1.10 Blueprint for cloud infrastructure deployment

The table below (Table 1) presents a step-by-step process for deploying both the GoTriple platform and each subsequent application that will be installed on the PCSS infrastructure as part of the LUMEN project.

Id	GoTriple migration	Future applications
1	Webinar on joining the PCSS	Meeting with PCSS employees -

⁴⁴ The SCRE core is based on Apache Camel, which is the Mediator. More about Apache Camel: <https://camel.apache.org/>.

	infrastructure as part of the GoTriple platform migration work.	preliminary assessment of technological and administrative needs.
2	Configuring access to the PCSS infrastructure - setting up LDAP accounts, creating a VPN instance.	Configuring access to the PCSS infrastructure - setting up LDAP accounts, creating a VPN instance.
3	Preparatory work around GoTriple – adapting to Kubernetes and OKD requirements. Improved performance of some application components.	Adapting the application for deployment to the infrastructure needs of PCSS PaaS - application optimization, creating Docker files, etc.
4	Creating Kubernetes objects - deployments, secrets, config-maps, etc.	Creating Kubernetes objects - deployments, secrets, config-maps, etc.
5	Configuring Docker images (conversion to Kubernetes-compatible images).	Configuring Docker images (conversion to Kubernetes-compatible images).
6	Database migration.	Deploying the application to the staging (test) environment.
7	ElasticSearch migration.	Database migration - first test migration (proof of concept), then the actual migration.
8	Migration of remaining components (activeMQ, etc.)	Establishing a backup plan, including a backup restoration plan.
9	Migration of the application's frontend layer.	Conducting performance tests.
10	Backup plan.	Security assessment, i.e., for example, deciding on the status of the application's exposure to the outside world, defining allowed IP addresses for connecting to individual services (whitelist), or creating a special repository for searching for vulnerabilities in images.
11	Security assessment.	Deploying the application to production.

12	Production deployment.	
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Table 1: Comparison of the GoTriple migration process with the deployment blueprint for future applications in LUMEN

The first column presents the most important steps taken in migrating the GoTriple platform – the starting point for developing a blueprint for subsequent applications in LUMEN.

The second column contains a comprehensive (also step-by-step) and analyzed (based on work related to GoTriple migration) outline for deploying other future applications in the LUMEN project.

3.2 PCSS PaaS capabilities in the context of technological development of applications and components in LUMEN

This section serves as a complement to the previous section (3.1). It provides valuable insights into the implementation of the PCSS PaaS infrastructure in the LUMEN project. The section primarily highlights further best practices in infrastructure management and opportunities to expand various infrastructure aspects, which can be effectively adapted to the evolving and dynamically changing needs of the LUMEN project.

3.2.1 Support for multiple components

Currently, the PCSS PaaS infrastructure includes two separate project spaces: one for the migrated GoTriple platform (the technological core of the White Label Platform – one of the most important components being developed within LUMEN) and the other for the emerging LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (LUMIS) application (a platform primarily used for ontology management, developed in Work Package 2).

However, other applications will be developed during the LUMEN project, such as the aforementioned White Label Platform and a range of advanced tools for researchers in various fields, such as a Meta Search Engine, metrics services, and Chatbot.

PCSS PaaS is prepared for this eventuality. Using the Kubernetes namespace concept, it ensures seamless creation of a new project per component. These projects remain isolated, but various communication modes can be established between them, as discussed in section 2.2.7. Each namespace also benefits from isolated resource quotas (CPU, memory, storage), ensuring predictable performance and preventing noisy-neighbour effects.

For example, the chatbot will rely on artificial intelligence technologies (especially LLMs) that may require GPU acceleration. The OKD cluster already includes GPU-enabled nodes and can be extended with additional GPU capacity if needed. Kubernetes natively manages GPU workloads through resource requests and scheduling rules, ensuring that applications requiring GPUs can be deployed without architectural changes. This capability has already been validated in practice through its use in the GRAPHIA project.

3.2.2 Development of the number of users

Similarly, the PCSS PaaS infrastructure can handle user traffic based on efficient expansion principles.

Currently, the development phase is underway, and the only users of LUMEN components are developers. Once tool and platform implementation are complete, there is nothing stopping target user traffic from significantly increasing. For example, if there are only 15 users today, tomorrow the infrastructure deployed in LUMEN could scale to tens of thousands of users, depending on the scaling rules and architecture of each component..

It is important to remember here (and this is also a valuable point in the context of section 3.2.1) the Kubernetes concept of only expanding when necessary. An example is memory expansion – in practice this is done through resource limits/requests or autoscaling mechanisms triggered by demand.

3.2.3 Expanding space

Resource expansion in Kubernetes refers to increasing the compute or storage resources assigned to an application. Compute resources (CPU, GPU and RAM) can be adjusted by updating the Deployment or StatefulSet, which triggers a controlled rolling update without interrupting the service.

Persistent storage (PVC) can also be expanded, depending on the capabilities of the underlying storage class. For example, an application may scale from 2 to 4 CPUs or increase its persistent volume from 20GB to 50GB as demand grows. These operations are performed directly through Kubernetes and do not require redesigning or redeploying the entire application.

3.2.4 Image repositories

The idea of image repositories, which are “a collection of related container images and tags identifying them”⁴⁵, is closely related to the concepts discussed earlier.

Container images, described in more detail in section 2.2.2, are relevant here.

Repositories also draw on the concept of encapsulation (isolation; see sections 2.2.7 and 3.2.1) of individual projects (repositories constitute closed spaces).

Working with repositories also serves as an example of best practices implemented in the context of application security. Repositories offer the ability to scan images and automatically detect vulnerabilities. Vulnerabilities are also mitigated by defining roles and user data access to specific images (using role-based access control (RBAC), described in section 2.2.3). Therefore, image repositories themselves constitute an important aspect of the Security by Design methodology.

3.2.5 PaaS for development

Using the Platform as a Service (PaaS) model inherently requires the use of good development practices. Working on the PCSS PaaS infrastructure is therefore automatically prepared for reliable and efficient application management at all levels.

The Security by Design methodology (described section 1.5.4) would be a good example here, as would using well-configured Docker images. To expand on one of the examples, it is worth focusing on Docker technology. Docker essentially enforces proper image configuration:

- it is recommended to use a lightweight base image and a minimal runtime environment – this will result in very fast image startup times, which is fantastic for performance reasons. For example, using distroless or alpine-based images significantly reduces attack surface and improves cold start time.
- when working with images, it is worth using a multi-stage build approach to separate the build environment from the runtime environment
- creating and using Kubernetes objects, such as ConfigMaps or Secrets, eliminates hardcoding variables
- it is also worth scanning the image for security before it's released to the repository—CI/CD practices are used for this purpose (described in more detail in section 1.5.3).

During the GoTriple platform migration, the best practices for working with Docker images described above were followed.

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https://docs.okd.io/latest/openshift_images/index.html#images-container-repository-about_overview-of-images

3.2.6 Different levels of access on the PCSS infrastructure

Interested developers from institutions participating in the LUMEN project consortium can obtain access to the PCSS PaaS infrastructure to work with individual project components. The detailed access granting process is described in section 3.1.2.

The infrastructure is structured around different access levels. Users can have different permissions within a given project space (role-based access control (RBAC) – see section 2.2.3). For LUMEN purposes, one user who has been granted access to the infrastructure (see section 3.1.2) holds the administrator role. This user therefore has all the possibilities (authorizations) in the context of a given project.

In the future, it will be possible to assign different roles that have more limited capabilities. Typical roles include admin, edit, and view, each with predefined capabilities aligned with RBAC.

3.2.7 Kubernetes and virtual machines

The PCSS PaaS infrastructure also provides scalable virtual machines (VMs, more on scalability in section 1.3.1), which can be essential for certain AI-related activities. VMs are useful for workloads that cannot be containerized, require full control over the operating system, or depend on custom drivers and libraries (e.g., specialized CUDA versions for AI training). They also support CPU- or GPU-intensive pipelines that need to run outside Kubernetes while still benefiting from the elasticity and scaling capabilities of the underlying cloud infrastructure.

4. Conclusion & next steps

The above chapters (1, 2, 3) present a plan – from general to detailed – for implementing the cloud infrastructure in the LUMEN project. The third chapter, devoted to migrating the GoTriple platform to PCSS servers, describes the comprehensive implementation of the component. Each deployment step has been expanded to provide the reader with an insight into the infrastructure development practice that is (and will continue to be) taking place within the LUMEN project.

Migrating a given component is one example of infrastructure activity. Another example is the arrangement of infrastructure space for newly developed components. The LUMIS

project is worth mentioning here, for which appropriate space has already been created, and the designated developers are already conducting appropriate implementation practices on the PCSS infrastructure.

Further work will include the ability to host components such as the White Label Platform, deployments of individual White Label instances, and applications such as Chatbot, visualization tools and Metrics Services.

Work is currently underway on installing the Software Catalogue – a collaboration between representatives of scientific disciplines and PCSS developers. This deliverable describes the possibility of seamless collaboration between the individual institutions that constitute the consortium's core. However, the LUMEN project also actively engages potential users (scientific domains), and collaboration in this context is also possible – as the Software Catalogue example demonstrates – at the infrastructure level.

Thanks to the resources and technological capabilities described in more detail in this deliverable, PCSS is able to ensure a stable and effective cloud infrastructure at every stage of the LUMEN project.

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